
Parent Item: 4 Ways Retrieval-augmented Generation (RAG) Is Revolutionizing Business Value from AI

Annotations

“all evidenced in the industry-specific examples below”

“Financial Services: Enhanced Risk Analysis”

“Healthcare: Precision Patient Care”

“Retail: Hyper-personalized Customer Support”

“Manufacturing: Real-time Supply Chain Optimization”

Parent Item: 6 Game-Changing RAG Use Cases: From Document Q&A to Real-Time AI

Annotations

“Smarter Document Question-Answering Systems”

“Context-Aware Conversational Agents”

“. SearchUnify has an LLM+RAG powered conversational agent for their users.”

“Real-Time Event Commentary AI”

“IBM leveraged the technology for commentary during the 2023 US Open”

“Hyper-Personalized Content Generation”

“Yarnit is an AI based content marketing platform that uses RAG for multiple tasks.”

“Supercharged Virtual Assistants”

Parent Item: 7 Practical Applications of RAG Models and their Impact on Society

Annotations

“Advanced Question-Answering Systems” s

“Content Creation and Summarization”

“Conversational Agents and Chatbots”

“Information Retrieval”

“Educational Tools and Resources”

“Legal Research and Analysis”

“Content Recommendation Systems”

Parent Item: 8 High-Impact Use Cases of RAG in Enterprises

Annotations

“At Signity Solutions, we have developed an AI-powered chatbot named Radbuddy focused on lung health. This system is built on the RAG framework to address the challenges faced by healthcare enterprises.

This RAG system not only generates an answer based on the training data but also pulls real-time data from the organization’s internal systems, such as diagnostic protocols and scheduled appointments.”

Parent Item: 9 powerful examples of retrieval-augmented generation (RAG)

Annotations

“Telescope, a sales automation platform, provides customers with recommendations on leads.”

“Help employees prepare for their upcoming interviews”

“Peoplelogic’s Growth Coordinator agent, “Noah”, can share relevant context on candidates based on the data in their ATS profiles”

“Generate actionable reports for sales leadership”

“Ema offers a Sales Intelligence Analyst agent that lets sales leaders create the reports they need through simple instructions”

“Offer insightful and actionable feedback from sales meetings”

“Surface the top issues and opportunities for product teams”

“Leverage information from a trusted online dictionary when giving feedback on copy”

“Answer a wide range of questions from employees”

“HR”

“Dora AI uses information from clients’ files in Assembly to deliver employees actionable insights.”

“Deliver high-fit candidate recommendations”

“Calculate key financial metrics and present them in a customizable model”

“financial”

“Causal’s users can uncover key financial metrics with the click of a button”

Parent Item: 10 RAG examples and use cases from real companies

Annotations

“Doordash, a food delivery company, enhances delivery support with a RAG-based chatbot.”

“developed an in-house solution”

“LLM Guardrail system, an online monitoring tool that evaluates each LLM-generated response for accuracy and compliance.”

“LLM Judge that assesses the chatbot's performance across five LLM evaluation metrics”

“support system.”

“Online professional platform LinkedIn introduced a novel customer service question-answering method that combines RAG with a knowledge graph.”

“LinkedIn's customer service team”

“Internal policies chatbot”

“Bell, a telecommunication services company, utilized RAG to enhance its knowledge management processes and ensure its employees have access to up-to-date company policies.”

“Harvard Business School's Senior Lecturer, Jeffrey Busgang, created a RAG-based AI faculty chatbot to help him teach his entrepreneurship course.”

“LLM judge to compare the outputs to the ground-truth data and generate a quality score.”

“Vimeo, a video hosting platform, enables users to converse with videos. The company developed a RAG-based chatbot that can summarize video content, link to key moments, and suggest additional questions.”

“Asian super-app Grab uses RAG-powered LLMs to automate routine analytical tasks like generating reports and performing fraud investigations.”

“fraud investigations”

“Business information and content technology provider”

“Thomson Reuters uses RAG to improve customer service. The company built a solution that helps customer support executives quickly access the most relevant information from a curated database in a chatty interface.”

“customer service”

“Discovery platform Pinterest helps internal company data users write SQL queries to solve analytical problems.”

“Pinterest”

“A fintech company Ramp used RAG to improve how they classified their customers and migrate to a standardized classification system.”

“To solve this problem, Ramp built an in-house RAG-based industry”

“The Royal Bank of Canada (RBC) built Arcane, a RAG system that points the bank’s specialists to the most relevant policies scattered across its internal web platform.”

“If you’re building a complex system like RAG, you need evaluations to test it during development and production monitoring.”

Parent Item: 10 RAG use cases and examples for businesses in 2025

Annotations

“Customer Support Automation”

“RAG-powered search tools cut through this mess”

“Contract Analysis and Legal Q&A”

“Financial Reporting & Analysis”

“HR and Onboarding Assistants”

“IT Support and Troubleshooting Bots”

“automatically generating and updating manuals, specs, and user guides straight from your actual codebase”

“reviewing company communications and internal records to flag compliance risks and generate audit summaries”

“Sales Enablement and RFP Automation”

“synthesizing scientific, market, and academic research from trusted sources”

Parent Item: 17 Best RAG Software Platforms for Rapid Deployment of GenAI Apps

Annotations

“ChatBees optimizes RAG for internal operations like customer support, employee support, etc.”

Parent Item: Build a "Corporate Brain" with RAG & Your Data Warehouse

Annotations

“an autonomous RAG agent on top of your existing data warehouse.” RAG Agent

“RAG for Structured Data”

“Most discussions about Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) focus on unstructured documents in a vector database. Our approach is different. For a data warehouse, the RAG process looks like this:

Retrieval: This isn't a vector search. The "retrieval" step is the generation and execution of a precise SQL query to fetch raw, structured data from the warehouse.

Augmentation: The raw data rows returned by the SQL query are "augmented" into the context of a final prompt for a Large Language Model (LLM).

Generation: The LLM "generates" a natural language summary of the data, directly answering the user's original question.

This distinction is critical. Success depends less on semantic similarity and more on the agent's ability to generate syntactically correct and logically sound SQL.” RAG system for structured data retrieval - data warehouse integration in LLM generation

“conversational AI layer for your data warehouse.”

Parent Item: chai+ | A Corporate RAG Solution

Annotations

“access to the information you need”

“handling internal and external inquiries”

“documents related to employment regulations and employee benefits”

Parent Item: Choosing the Best RAG Technique for Meetings

Annotations

“enhance meeting insights, streamline decision-making, and improve knowledge management”

“A query like, “Which product category saw the highest revenue growth?” no longer requires digging through reports—it’s answered instantly, with supporting data from internal databases and external market trends.”

Parent Item: Die Gewinner der Enterprise RAG Challenge

Annotations

“Effiziente semantische Suche mit LLM-gestützter Optimierung”

“Cleverer Kombination aus Embeddings & LLMs für präzise Antworten”

“Hohe Präzision durch mehrstufige Verarbeitung, Konsistenzprüfung und LLM-gestütztes Reranking”

“Cleverer Kombination aus Embeddings & LLMs für präzise Antworten”

“Intelligentes Retrieval, Adaptives Matching & LLM-gesteuerte Antwortgenerierung”

“Hohe Präzision durch mehrstufige Verarbeitung, Konsistenzprüfung und LLM-gestütztes Reranking”

“Mehrstufiges Retrieval mit LLM-Optimierung für bessere Antwortqualität”

Parent Item: Enterprise RAG System: Best Practices Strategies

Annotations

“handles massive amounts of data to provide actionable insights into China’s political economy”

“AI-powered recommendation system, the “step suggester,” to assist students in cybersecurity coursework. This tool offers real-time guidance to students facing challenges, improving course completion rates.”

“AI chatbot data extraction solution using ChatGPT to help an NGO quickly retrieve information on gun safety from their extensive knowledge base.”

Parent Item: Examples of RAG: use cases and companies that can benefit from it

Annotations

“personalized responses”

“It goes beyond pre-written interactions, helping companies to share personalized answers with their customers based on their needs.”

“personalized messages, advertising texts and promotional content”

“personalized materials”

“generate reports or summaries on patients' health”

“personalizing search results to creating personalized product recommendations”

Parent Item: Exploring RAG and Grounding Use Cases

Annotations

“Grounding”

“ntelligent Knowledge Bases and Q&A Systems”

“nternal IT Support”

“Customer Service Agents”

“HR Self-Service”

“Augmented Business Intelligence and Reporting”

“Grounding is the critical objective of anchoring LLM outputs in factual, context-specific data”

Parent Item: Harnessing corporate knowledge with AI | Datacidars

Annotations

“In the past, one of our customers had to wade through mountains of documents to find answers to such questions, investing a lot of time and nerves.”

“interactive chatbot,”

“experiencing an ever-increasing range of data to be integrated within individual customer projects”

“challenge when integrating your own data into RAG applications lies in the internal structure of the documents. Typical documentation texts contain not only plain text, but also many illustrations, such as diagrams, drawings or photos, tables, cross-references, warnings and the like”

Parent Item: Harnessing RAG in Healthcare: Use-Cases, Impact, & Solutions | HatchWorks AI

Annotations

“Clinical Decision Support Systems”

“s Apollo 24|7, a digital healthcare platform that uses Google’s MedPaLM augmented with RAG to build a Clinical Intelligence Engine (CIE).”

“Medical Research and Knowledge Management”

“Patient Engagement and Communication”

“Operational Efficiency and Workflow Optimization”

Parent Item: How RAG Can Help Your Business Grow in 2025

Annotations

“Chatbots”

“Onboarding”

“securely accessing and providing sensitive information when needed while ensuring compliance with regulations like GDPR”

“Information Retrieval”

Parent Item: How RAG is revolutionizing business decision-making | Invisible Blog

Annotations

“Rui Bai, Product Manager of AI and Machine Learning at Invisible Technologies.”

““If you’re an investment bank or professional services firm, you operate in a ‘zero-error’ environment,” Bai explains. “You can’t have an LLM hallucinate and give you an unfactual answer when millions of dollars are at stake.””

“Bai says Invisible has already helped an investment bank implement a proto-version of RAG using a model trained on an initial test set of the firm’s documents. Bankers can use a chat interface to get instant answers to any questions based on these documents.”

“links to original sources so that users can verify the outputs and ensure the information is always correct.”

Parent Item: Interesting Gen AI RAG use cases that can deliver quick impact

Annotations

“Q&A support in L1/L2 in customer service operations.”

“Compliance in customer contact centers”

“Employee knowledge training assessment for talent management”

“Global SOP Standardization and Legal documents”

“identifying variations in existing contracts and also help during renewal or new contracts being created”

“Operations support assistant (manufacturing and maintenance)”

Parent Item: Key Use Cases of RAG: From Chatbots to Research Assistants

Annotations

“banking chatbot using RAG can fetch the latest interest rates, loan policies, and customer queries”

“e-commerce chatbot using RAG can pull the latest product details, return policies, and order tracking updates”

“news website using RAG can retrieve recent stock market trends and economic updates before generating investment reports”

“research assistant AI using RAG can fetch the latest medical studies and research papers, helping doctors and scientists stay updated”

“egal AI assistant using RAG can fetch recent court rulings and government policies, helping lawyers with up-to-date insights.”

“telehealth assistant using RAG can fetch updated disease treatment protocols and drug safety warnings, ensuring accurate patient guidance.”

Parent Item: KI Anwendungsfälle unserer Kunden

Annotations

“Eine multimodale, RAG basierte Knowledge Plattform wurde implementiert: Zentrale Retrieval Oberfläche für alle Quellen. Semantische Interpretation komplexer Dokumente. Content Generierung strikt CD konform. Personas sorgen für individuellen Schreibstil.”

Parent Item: Outshift | Supercharge productivity: 5 retrieval-augmented generation use cases

Annotations

“Enhanced content crafting with RAG”

“RAG-driven market intelligence”

“Chat with data”

“dynamic approach can significantly enhance customer engagement by providing personalized experiences that resonate with the ever-changing preferences of the audience.”

“o bring new employees up to speed or help customers understand products and services”

Parent Item: Practical Use Cases of Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG)

Annotations

“Shopify: Their Sidekick chatbot leverages RAG to deliver superior AI customer service, offering precise answers related to products, account issues, and troubleshooting.”

“DoorDash: Uses a RAG-based system to enhance delivery support for its "Dashers," quickly condensing issues and retrieving relevant articles to provide accurate solutions .”

“Siemens: Utilizes RAG technology to enhance its internal knowledge management, allowing employees to retrieve information from various internal documents and databases quickly.”

“Bell: Uses RAG to ensure employees have access to up-to-date company policies, processing and indexing raw documents efficiently .”

“Mayo Clinic: A leader in leveraging RAG for real-time clinical decision support, assisting doctors in retrieving critical information during patient assessments.”

“Allianz Bank Italy: Implements RAG to streamline customer consultations, enabling financial consultants to access real-time, relevant data from internal documents and regulatory guidelines, improving accuracy and reducing search time.”

“NatWest: Uses the RAG-powered assistant Marge to provide faster, more accurate responses to both customers and internal teams, optimizing service delivery and operational speed.”

“Vectara: Vectara utilizes Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) to enable product teams and researchers to quickly access patents, scientific literature, and market intelligence, thereby streamlining innovation and accelerating product development.”

“Microsoft: Uses RAG in research and product development to ensure teams have real-time access to the latest scientific findings and industry trends.”

“Bloomberg: Uses RAG to process and summarize financial documents, reports, and news articles, allowing analysts to gain insights and stay up-to-date with real-time market changes quickly.”

Parent Item: RAG (Retrieval Augmented Generation) on Databricks | Databricks on AWS

Annotations

“answer domain-specific questions”

Parent Item: RAG 2025: KI mit Unternehmensdaten trainieren | Enterprise RAG & Vector Databases

Annotations

“Support-Bot kann Antworten direkt aus aktuellen Handbüchern zitieren”

“Chatbots”

“Compliance-Abteilung helfen RAG-Systeme, Klauseln in Verträgen zu prüfen oder Richtlinien automatisch gegenzulesen”

“interne Wissensassistenten”

“ultimodalen RAG-Systemen”

“Statt Antworten nur aus Trainingsdaten zu erzeugen, greift die KI auf aktuelle Informationen wie Dokumente, Verträge oder interne Wissensdatenbanken zurück. So entstehen faktenbasierte und überprüfbare Ergebnisse.”

“Halluzinationen”

“Daten bestmöglich nutzbar”

Parent Item: RAG and LLM business process automation: A technical strategy

Annotations

“A multinational company exports electronic goods globally. Using RAG, the company accesses up-to-date trade regulations for each destination. Before dispatching a shipment, RAG validates it against these regulations and auto-generates the necessary documentation.”

“The Grid Dynamics Intelligent Document Processing Starter Kit demonstrates how LLMs and RAG can be used to generate responses to RFPs based on general company information and product specifications.” Automatic form filling

“By processing years of procurement data, RAG can identify which suppliers consistently meet quality standards, deliver on time, and offer competitive prices. This allows the manufacturer to prioritize partnerships with high-performing vendors and potentially negotiate better terms.”

“RAG then compiles a detailed report that not only highlights how the retailer performed in previous years but also predicts potential challenges for the upcoming season.”

“retailers can empower chatbots to fetch specific product details from vast databases in near real-time, enhancing customer queries’ responsiveness and accuracy.”

“aggregate feedback from various channels, interpret the sentiment, and identify if there are recurrent issues or praises about particular product features”

“Marketing campaign analysis”

“Personalized recommendations”

RAG harnesses customer data, including past purchases and browsing history, to understand individual preferences”

“A high-net-worth client, looking to diversify their portfolio, uses the bank’s chat interface to inquire about potential investment opportunities in emerging markets. With RAG-powered chatbots, the system instantly combs through a plethora of global economic reports, past performance metrics of emerging market funds, and current geopolitical trends.”

“By implementing RAG, as soon as a policyholder submits a claim, the system can instantly fetch the policy details, compare the claim with previous ones, and even provide an immediate tentative evaluation based on existing policy guidelines and historical claim data. This rapid response not only expedites the claim processing but also significantly enhances the customer experience, especially during stressful post-accident scenarios.”

“However, with RAG, the moment financial data gets updated in the central system, it fetches relevant data points from various sources, compares them against past performances, and incorporates macroeconomic indicators. The result is an automatically generated comprehensive financial report that highlights trends, potential concerns, and areas of growth.”

“Using a platform powered by RAG, their financial advisor can swiftly assess past investment decisions, current market dynamics, and the investor’s risk profile. RAG then provides a rebalanced portfolio recommendation, advising on which assets to retain, potential sectors for new investments, and the ideal bond-stock mix.”

“Document loading”

“Document splitting”

Parent Item: RAG Explained: Why Retrieval-Augmented Generation Matters

Annotations

“Intelligente Produktsuche”

“Personalisierung und Empfehlungen”

“Automatisierte Produkt- und Content-Erstellung”

“Datengetriebene Content-Erstellung”

“Unterstützung bei Markt- und Kundenanalysen”

“SEO und Sichtbarkeit”

“Kreativität und Kampagnenentwicklung”

“Fortschrittliche Chatbots”

“Google integriert es in AI Overviews”

“Microsoft in Bing Chat”

Parent Item: RAG for Technology: Use-Cases, Impact, & Solutions | HatchWorks AI

Annotations

“Code Generation and Completion”

“Debugging with Enhanced Efficiency”

“Data Retrieval for Model Training and Analysis”

“Automating Feature Engineering”

“Real-Time Threat Detection”

“Enhancing Incident Response Systems”

Parent Item: RAG Meaning in Business: Complete 2025 Guide

Annotations

“AI4Legal – RAG in service of law and compliance”

“minimizes the risk of errors,”

“AI4Content – intelligent content creation with RAG”

“factual mistakes”

“AI4E-learning – personalized training powered by RAG”

“AI4Knowledge Base – intelligent knowledge management for enterprises”

“AI4Localisation – automated translation and content localization”

“mplementations depends heavily on the quality, accuracy, and currency of underlying information sources”

“Data consistency challenges arise when information exists across multiple systems with different formats, terminology, or”

Parent Item: RAG Systems: what are they and how can they benefit the insurance industry?

Annotations

“insurance industry”

“1. Chatbot and virtual assistant optimization”

“2. Efficiency in sales processes.”

“3. Improved evaluation of internal information and reduced processing times.”

Parent Item: RAG Use Cases: Enhance AI, ML Workflows Efficiently

Annotations

“find the documents, tasks, or notes you need across your entire workspace and connected apps”

Parent Item: RAG: 5 Anwendungsfälle für die Verbindung aus GenAI und Unternehmenswissen

Annotations

“RAG zur Informationsextraktion”

“RAG zur Generierung von Inhalten”

“RAG im Kundensupport”

“RAG im Wissensmanagement”

“RAG in der Marktanalyse”

Parent Item: RAG: GenAI trifft Unternehmenswissen | ATVANTAGE

Annotations

“Zum Beispiel hat eine Versicherung mithilfe von RAG einen Bot entwickelt, der automatisiert und individuell auf Sachstandsfragen aus E-Mails oder Call-Center-Ereignissen antwortet, und zwar im spezifischen Kommunikationsstil der Versicherung.”

“spezifischen Kommunikationsstil der Versicherung.”

“Unternehmens-GPT”

Parent Item: RAG: How Advanced AI is Changing the Game for Businesses

Annotations

“They can integrate RAG with its internal database of product manuals, technical specifications, and troubleshooting guides, so that customer support agents can quickly access relevant information to address customer inquiries.”

“chatbots beyond standard FAQs.”

“Medical staff can use RAG-powered search tools to quickly access patient records, medical guidelines, and research articles, significantly reducing the time spent searching for relevant information.”

Parent Item: RAG: Smarter AI for Business Data | Uptech

Annotations

“Apollo 24|7, a healthcare platform that integrated Google’s MedPaLM with RAG to build a Clinical Intelligence Engine (CIE). The system gives clinicians access to de-identified patient data, recent studies, and treatment guidelines. All this information is retrieved and summarized in real time to support diagnostic decisions.”

“Arcane, a RAG-based chatbot”

“Grab, a multi-service platform in Asia, built a RAG-based system that connects LLMs with internal APIs and prompt templates to generate summaries and reports automatically. These reports are delivered directly in Slack, and Grab claims this saves around 3-4 hours of manual work per report.”

Parent Item: Retrieval Augmentation for Smarter Business Decisions | Hyland

Annotations

From the FAQs:

Hyland leverages Knowledge Discovery internally and on Hyland Community, our training portal. We use Knowledge Discovery to empower customers and employees to quickly find answers across help documentation, incident histories and knowledge articles.

“AI-powered search and natural language queries”

“AI-powered search”

“Smarter decision support”

Parent Item: Retrieval Augmented Generation

Annotations

“JetBlue has deployed "BlueBot," a chatbot that uses open source generative AI models complemented by corporate data, powered by Databricks. This chatbot can be used by all teams at JetBlue to get access to data that is governed by role. For example, the finance team can see data from SAP and regulatory filings, but the operations team will only see maintenance information.”

“Chevron Phillips Chemical uses Databricks to support their generative AI initiatives, including document process automation.”

“Thrivent Financial is looking at generative AI to make search better, produce better summarized and more accessible insights, and improve the productivity of engineering.”

Parent Item: Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) – 5 Use Cases

Annotations

“Boosting Customer Support with RAG-Enabled Chatbots”

“Enhancing AI Avatars with Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG)”

“Speeding Up the Onboarding of New Employees”

“Enhancing Content Creation”

“Customer Feedback Analysis with RAG”

Parent Item: Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) Examples & Best Practices – ValueMiner

Annotations

“To help our customers solve this urgent issue, we combined ValueMiner role-based data access control with RAG. It restricts information for AI assistants based on a user’s role within your company, enhancing governance compliance and operational efficiency.

With role-based access and retrieval augmented generation RAG, AI assistants deliver accurate information based on both business knowledge and user roles, ensuring only authorized employees see sensitive data, just like real-world business operations.

The benefits? Data stays secure, compliance is assured, and employees get the precise information they need.”

Parent Item: Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG): Chat mit eigenen Daten

Annotations

“Halluzinationen zu vermeiden und zuverlässiger zu antworten”

“Fragen zu internen Dokumenten und/oder anderen Daten mithilfe eines Large Language Models zu beantworten”

“mit eigenen Dokumenten bzw. Daten zu chatten.”

“semantischen Suche”

“Elasticsearch, OpenSearch oder Apache Solr”

“Sensible Daten mit einem Open-Source LLM verarbeiten”

“Wir haben gute Erfahrungen mit dem Einsatz zweier LLMs innerhalb einer RAG Pipeline gemacht”

Parent Item: Retrieval Augmented Generation and its corporate usage

Annotations

“Paradigma, we have leveraged the power of RAG to build advanced AI solutions tailored to our specific business needs and those of our clients”

“For internal purposes,”

“Google Cloud's Retrieval-Augmented Generation capabilities to develop a Generative AI-powered internal chatbot.”

“AWS, we developed a Generative AI tool specifically designed for contact centers”

“This tool enables agents to retrieve real-time information about competitors' current offers during customer conversations”

“contact centers”

“Azure-based solutions, we created an advanced tool for a large fashion retailer that vectorizes their existing APIs”

“IT support”

Parent Item: Retrieval Augmented Generation use cases for enterprise

Annotations

“An LLM’s knowledge is frozen when pre-training (or any fine-tuning) ends. Any subsequent information, whether regulatory updates, product launches, or market changes, is inaccessible to the model unless it undergoes another training cycle, which is costly and time-consuming.”

“At indigo.ai, we have developed a cutting-edge RAG pipeline designed to seamlessly integrate external knowledge sources into every conversational interaction. By combining advanced retrieval methods with next-generation generative models, our system ensures that each user query receives a response based on the most relevant and up-to-date information available. This robust and modular architecture not only improves the accuracy and reliability of answers but also enables clear citation of the sources used, making our AI Agents dynamic, transparent and truly trustworthy tools.”

“enterprise search engines and internal assistants”

“A concrete example comes from the financial sector”

“E-commerce and product recommendation”

“AI Agents for customer support”

“In healthcare, RAG is being tested to develop clinical assistants that can consult guidelines, hospital protocols and scientific literature, helping doctors and medical staff with evidence-aligned and trustworthy answers.”

Parent Item: Retrieval augmented generation use cases: Transforming data into insights

Annotations

“Machine translation”

“Question answering”

“Summarization”

Parent Item: Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) Examples and Use Cases

Annotations

“Finance <https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.11944>
Legal <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.11325>
Medicine <https://arxiv.org/html/2402.13178v2>
Healthcare <https://arxiv.org/abs/2403.09226>
Technology <https://arxiv.org/html/2404.00657v1>
Agriculture <https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.08406>
Pharmaceuticals <https://arxiv.org/html/2402.01717v1>
Telecommunications <https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.15939>
Energy <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.06566>
Science <https://arxiv.org/abs/2403.15729>
Education <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.07796>
Construction <https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.09939>
Sport <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.01280>
Real Estate <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.01429>”

“Text

Text-based modalities represent the vast majority of RAG use cases. They include:

QA: Generating answers to user questions based upon a repository of textual sources.

Summarization: Distill the essential information from longer texts.

Fact Verification: Determining whether a given claim can be supported by facts in the text.

Commonsense Reasoning: The capability of machines to infer in a human-like manner, drawing upon external knowledge.

Human-Machine Conversation: A language model using external data sources to maintain a human-like conversation for the purposes of a goal.

Translation: An automated process of translating text from a source language to a target language.

Extraction: A goal in natural language processing that involves identifying and categorizing specific events and entities within a text and associating them via relevant relationships.

Recommendations: Using RAG to help recommend in natural language.

Generation: Using retrieval to help generative tasks based upon an external database, like a blog, for example.

Classification: Classify items based upon how other items in a repository have been classified.

Search: Combining interpretation with retrieval to find items in a repository of information.”

“Code

Code-related use cases were subtly different compared to text-based approaches:

Generation: Convert natural language descriptions into code implementations.

Summarization: Convert code into natural languages descriptions.

Completion: Predict the next bit of code.

Automatic Program Repair: Query-based RAG is often used in automatic program repair to help generative models fix buggy codes.

Generation: Generating and running new code to perform a deeper analysis.

Testing & Security: Using language models and RAG to perform functional and security testing, like fuzzing and prompt injection.”

“Databases

Databases are a natural source of data, so it has become common to interface language models with them:

Translation: Conversion of natural language into database specific query languages like SQL.

Graph-Based QA: Leveraging graph databases like knowledge bases to answer a question, often via generating database specific queries like SPARQL.

Table-Based QA: Using relation databases or spreadsheets to answer questions based upon structured knowledge. Often includes generative code aspects to answer more complicated queries.”

“Media

These tasks generally apply to image, video, and audio modalities. It could even include more esoteric data formats like 3D data:

Generation: Generation usually refers to the models generating new media. But in a RAG context, it refers to the use of external repositories of media to help guide or seed the generation.

Captioning: Captioning is the process of generating a textual descriptions of media. For example, adding subtitles or image captions. In a RAG context, this refers to leveraging external text or media to improve the captioning process.

QA: This refers to asking questions based upon the media followed by retrieval. For example, ‘who wrote this song?’.”

“Science

Generative techniques are also being applied to the sciences. Where there is a repository of information, it makes sense to include RAG in the process:

Drug discovery: Generate molecules that fulfill requirements.

Medical Applications: Improve the generation of a language model by retrieving information from biomedical domain-specific databases.

Maths: Streamline problem-solving, boost innovation and refine educational strategies.”

Parent Item: Retrieval-Augmented Generation for Business

Annotations

“re-ranking phase”

“optimized and personalized response”

“refining the precision of retrieval and re-ranking processes will remain a priority”

“optimize algorithms and ranking models”

Parent Item: Securing Knowledge with RAG: From Data Chaos to Corporate Knowledge

Annotations

“collective capital”

“This way, employees receive precise answers within seconds to complex questions regarding processes, system errors, or historical decisions, significantly improving troubleshooting, compliance queries, and the analysis of incident logs.”

“onboarding is accelerated: verified, company-specific knowledge is immediately available”

“At CURE,”

“we already use RAG successfully. This allows us to systematically capture individual knowledge, make it structurally accessible, and keep it immediately usable for all employees.”

Parent Item: The Promise of RAG: Bringing Enterprise Generative AI to Life

Annotations

“Employee productivity apps – Assist employees in finding and leveraging existing organizational knowledge buried across databases, emails, and documents.”

“Analysis assistants – Provide insights to employees through document summarization or Q&A”

“Employee training tools – Help onboard”

“Customer support chatbots”

“Public-facing Q&A systems”

“AI21’s RAG Engine offers enterprises an all-in-one solution for implementing Retrieval-Augmented Generation”

Parent Item: Top 7 examples of retrieval-augmented generation

Annotations

“Customer support chatbots”

“Content generation and summarization”

“Enterprise Q&A systems”

“Healthcare and clinical decision support”

“Financial services and compliance”

“Legal research and contract review”

Parent Item: Top 7 RAG Use Cases and Applications to Explore in 2025

Annotations

“Customer Support Chatbots”

“Shopify’s Sidekick chatbot”

“In the finance sector, Bloomberg has implemented RAG”

“decision-making for analysts by providing real-time summaries tailored to current financial context”

“IBM Watson for Oncology was able to match treatment recommendations with expert oncologists 96%”

“RAMO (Retrieval-Augmented Generation for MOOCs),”

“JPMorgan Chase make use of AI-driven fraud detection systems using Retrieval-Augmented Generation RAG models.”

“e, Amazon has integrated AI-driven recommendation engines that utilize Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) techniques to enhance e-commerce product recommendations”

“Siemens utilizes Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) technology to enhance internal knowledge management”

“Another notable application is at Morgan Stanley, which uses Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) technology in its Wealth Management division to enhance its internal knowledge”

Parent Item: Top 10 RAG Use Cases and 17 Essential Tools for Implementation

Annotations

“Quickly access onboarding materials and resources be it for customers, or internal employees like support, sales, or research team.”

“Easily find product information and customer data”

“Respond to customer inquiries promptly and accurately”

“Quick access to project data, bug reports, discussions, and resources, fostering efficient collaboration.”

“immediate search, chat, and summarization”

Parent Item: Top 10 RAG Use Cases and Business Benefits | Uptech

Annotations

“Advanced Question-Answering Systems”

“BioRAGent, an interactive biomedical QA system, demonstrates how scientists can pose complex questions and receive answers linked to source snippets from PubMed.”

“Another system, PaperQA, was evaluated on PubMedQA, a benchmark of biomedical questions.”

“Virtual assistants”

“EVEE Intelligent Q&A, a GenAI solution built on RAG. EVEE allows specialists to ask questions and instantly receive concise answers drawn from internal documentation.”

“Bloomberg applies the RAG approach to financial transcripts and earnings reports” Already covered in other article

“Medical Diagnostics and Research” Also covered by another article

“IBM Watson for Oncology” Already covered in other article

“Beyond the lab, Mastercard has already applied RAG-based voice scam detection in production, reaching a 300% increase in detection rates.”

“Ramp, a fintech company, shows how this works in practice. Their team replaced a fragmented, homegrown classification method with an RAG-based assistant that uses the NAICS standard.”

“RAG opens new possibilities for drug discovery because it solves one of the field’s biggest hurdles: the need to keep AI models updated with fast-growing biochemical data.” It seems as if this is not a fully deployed use case yet

“A study by HR Bartender found that 64% of new hires decide whether to stay or leave within the first 45 days. A SHRM study in 2024 found that companies using advanced onboarding solutions helped employees reach full productivity 33% faster than those without structured support.”

“IT Support and Troubleshooting Bots”

“Presidio Investors, a US-based fintech company that needed to automate the processing of investment data. We designed a secure system that uses AI to extract key details from emails and attachments, transform them into structured data, and update the CRM automatically. The result was an 80% reduction in manual work and the ability to process up to 100 investment deals each day.”

Parent Item: Top 13 RAG as a service use cases your business needs

Annotations

“Smart internal FAQ assistant”

“Customer support for SaaS”

“Vendor finder for procurement”

“Marketing assistant for content teams”

“Real-time financial advisor”

“Legal document analyzer”

“Field manual assistant”

“Retail analytics portal”

“Agribusiness decision engine”

“Pharmaceutical research assistant”

“Insurance claims reviewer”

“Personalized learning coach”

“Smart compliance advisor”

Parent Item: Top 14 RAG Use Cases You Need to Know in 2025

Annotations

“Code Generation and Software Development”

“GitHub CoPilot uses RAG for code suggestions”

“Customer Service Automation”

“Zendesk uses RAG for smarter ticket resolution.”

“Sales Assistance and Lead Scoring”

“Salesforce uses RAG to provide insights on leads.”

“Email Drafting and Management”

“Grammarly uses RAG to adjust the email tone.”

“Financial Forecasting and Analysis”

“Bloomberg Terminal for market insights.”

“Legal Document Review”

“LexisNexis applies RAG for legal analysis.”

“Content Creation and Optimization”

“Jasper uses RAG to create content.”

“HR Onboarding and Recruitment”

“LinkedIn uses RAG for talent matching.”

“Personalized Marketing Campaigns”

“HubSpot integrates RAG for personalized campaigns”

“Supply Chain and Logistics Planning”

“DHL uses RAG for optimizing delivery routes”

“Healthcare Diagnosis Assistance”

“IBM Watson Health uses RAG for medical insights.”

“Educational Tutoring and Learning Support”

“Pearson uses RAG for adaptive learning.”

“Project Management Assistance”

“Asana leverages RAG for task insights.”

“Meeting Summaries and Transcriptions”

“Otter.ai uses RAG to enhance transcripts.”

Parent Item: Understanding the RAG Pattern in AI and Its Use Cases

Annotations

“Customer Support Systems”

“Research Assistance”

“Healthcare Applications”

“Legal Document Review”

“Educational Tools”

“Content Generation for SEO”

Parent Item: Was ist RAG? — Wie Retrieval Augmented Generation Ihr Unternehmen voranbringen kann

Annotations

“Zugriff auf interne Dokumente”

“Rechts- und Compliance-Beratung”

“KI-gestützter Kundensupport:”

“Spaces”

Parent Item: What is RAG (Retrieval Augmented Generation) [+ Examples]

Annotations

“During the webinar, we explored how Databricks is pioneering the use of large language models (LLMs) in creating advanced documentation chatbots. These bots are designed to simplify the search for information by providing direct access to relevant documents.”

“Databricks' use case extends into personalized information retrieval, harnessing the full potential of LLMs. By doing so, the system not only provides general documentation but also adapts its responses to fit the user's specific needs, paving the way for a revolution in user support interactions.”

Parent Item: What is RAG (retrieval augmented generation) | McKinsey

Annotations

“Enterprise-knowledge-management chatbot.”

“Customer service chatbots.”

“Drafting assistants.”

“QuantumBlack, AI by McKinsey.”

Parent Item: What Is RAG? Use Cases, Limitations, and Challenges

Annotations

“Customer Support Automation”

“Legal and Financial Services”

“Research and Content Creation”

“Conversational Agents and Chatbots”

Parent Item: What is Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG)?

Annotations

“Semantic search is a data-searching technique that helps AI systems understand the meaning and intent of a query. It uses natural language processing (NLP) to go deeper than keyword search. Instead of matching the words in the query, semantic search breaks down the meaning of words and phrases in order to retrieve the most relevant results.

To generate precise results when analyzing the semantic similarity between words, semantic search relies on vector search. Vector search turns individual words, phrases, and documents into vectors—a numeric representation of data—as points in multidimensional space. Things that are closely related in meaning (e.g., backpack, knapsack) have vectors that are positioned more closely together in space. In this way, during a vector search, a query is transformed into a vector in order to search for nearby vectors in multidimensional space. The more closely positioned they are, the more relevant they are to one another.”

“AI CHATBOTS”

“Personalized Recommendations”

“Live Conversation Intelligence”

“Supply Chain Optimization”

“Decision Support”

Parent Item: What Is Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)?

Annotations

“financial services company could draw on customer information to surface relevant insights for representatives”

“healthcare field could answer a patient's questions and help schedule the best provide”

“In manufacturing, an autonomous agent could be used to monitor equipment and optimize production processes”

“And in the auto industry, a RAG AI agent could help across the board, doing everything from creating promotions based on real-time inventory levels to proactively surfacing vehicle maintenance issues.”

Parent Item: What is Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)? A Practical Guide

Annotations

“Retrieval-augmented generation challenges”

“chatbot response”

“Respond to Data Subject Access Requests (DSARs) from customers.”

“Identify fraudulent customer activity.”

“A stock investor wishing to see the commissions she was charged over the last quarter”

“A hospital patient wanting to compare the drugs he received to the payments he made”

“A telco subscriber choosing a new Internet-TV-phone plan since his is about to terminate”

“A car owner requesting a 3-year insurance claim history to reduce her annual premium”

“inform army veterans about reimbursement policies”

Parent Item: What is Retrieval-Augmented Generation?

Annotations

“Enterprise Search and Internal Q&A.”

“Customer Support and Chatbots”

“Compliance and Legal Review.”

“Research and Insights Generation.”